

Appendix

“How Perceptions of Voter Control Affect Politicians’ Evaluations of Mass-Mediated Expert Advice: A Survey Experiment on the Role of Accountability Beliefs”

Response rate

Table A1 Calculation of politicians' response rate

	Code	N
<i>Interview</i>		
Complete	1.0/1.10	1,161
Partial	1.2000	30
<i>Eligible, non-interview</i>		
Opt-out via link or e-mail	2.1110	180
Clicked on survey but no response recorded	2.1120	69
Partial surveys not used for this paper	2.1200	135
<i>Unknown eligibility, non-interview</i>		
No response via e-mail/click/response	3.1000	937
No valid e-mail address available	3.1100	5
<i>Total sample used</i>		
I=Complete interviews	1.1	1,161
P=Partial interviews	1.2	30
R=Refusal and break off	2.1	384
NC=Non-contact	2.2	0
O=Other	2.0/2.3	0
UH=Unknown household	3.1	941
UO=Unknown other	3.2-3.9	0
Response Rate 1		46.1%
Response Rate 2		47.2%

Note: Response rates are calculated based on the AAPOR Response Rate Calculator V4.0. I assumed a proportion of 100% for unknown eligibility because I relied on address lists provided by the parliamentary services. I considered the final address lists from the parliamentary services as the total population (N=2,517). Four newly elected members of parliament (MPs) (who were not yet on the list of MPs) contacted the project team to take part in the survey and were included as well. Therefore, the total population consisted of 2,521 MPs.

Experimental manipulations

Table A2 Number of observations in the experimental conditions

Condition	Statement manipulation	n
3	Academic x Opinion-based x High Advocacy x Flu vaccination	99
4	Academic x Opinion-based x High Advocacy x Colorectal cancer screening	95
5	Academic x Evidence-based x Low Advocacy x Flu vaccination	102
6	Academic x Evidence-based x Low Advocacy x Colorectal cancer screening	99
9	Administration x Opinion-based x Low Advocacy x Flu vaccination	97
12	Administration x Opinion-based x High Advocacy x Colorectal cancer screening	93
14	Administration x Evidence-based x Low Advocacy x Colorectal cancer screening	100
15	Administration x Evidence-based x High Advocacy x Flu vaccination	102
17	Corporation x Opinion-based x Low Advocacy x Flu vaccination	102
18	Corporation x Opinion-based x Low Advocacy x Colorectal cancer screening	97
23	Corporation x Evidence-based x High Advocacy x Flu vaccination	105
24	Corporation x Evidence-based x High Advocacy x Colorectal cancer screening	100

Fig. A1 Presentation of the expert quote

Note: This image is a screenshot from the online survey, which was conducted using the Qualtrics software.

Table A3 Wording of experimental treatments (translated)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Values</i>	<i>Flu vaccination</i>	<i>Colorectal cancer screening</i>
Type of expert	Academic	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get a flu vaccination. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss university</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of vaccinations: , said the expert from the <i>university</i> .	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get colorectal cancer screening tests. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss university</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of cancer prevention: , said the expert from the <i>university</i> .
	Administration	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get a flu vaccination. The following quote from <i>an expert from the responsible federal agency</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of vaccinations: , said the expert from the <i>federal agency</i> .	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get colorectal cancer screening tests. The following quote from <i>an expert from the responsible federal agency</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of cancer prevention: , said the expert from the <i>federal agency</i> .
	Pharma	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get a flu vaccination. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss pharmaceutical company</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of vaccinations: , said the expert from the <i>pharmaceutical company</i> .	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get colorectal cancer screening tests. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss pharmaceutical company</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of cancer prevention: , said the expert from the <i>pharmaceutical company</i> .
Evidence base	Evidence-based	<i>According to current figures</i> , several hundred people die from influenza every year. The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths. <i>Studies show</i> that flu vaccination can effectively reduce the number of flu cases.	<i>According to current figures</i> , almost two thousand people die from colorectal cancer every year. The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths. <i>Studies show</i> that colorectal cancer screening tests can effectively reduce the number of colorectal cancer cases.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Values</i>	<i>Flu vaccination</i>	<i>Colorectal cancer screening</i>
		<i>The data also confirm</i> that serious side effects due to influenza vaccination are very rare.	<i>The data also confirm</i> that serious side effects due to colorectal cancer screening tests are very rare.
	Opinion-based	<p><i>I estimate</i> that several hundred people die from the flu every year.</p> <p>The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths.</p> <p><i>I am convinced</i> that flu vaccination can effectively reduce the number of flu cases.</p> <p><i>As far as I know</i>, serious side effects of the flu vaccination are very rare.</p>	<p><i>I estimate</i> that almost two thousand people die from colorectal cancer every year.</p> <p>The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths.</p> <p><i>I am convinced</i> that colorectal cancer screening tests can effectively reduce the number of colorectal cancer cases.</p> <p><i>As far as I know</i>, serious side effects due to colorectal cancer screening tests are very rare.</p>
Degree of advocacy	High	It is therefore imperative that politicians invest more money in information campaigns, because this means that more people from risk groups and from the latter's environment will take advantage of vaccination.	It is therefore imperative that politicians invest more money in information campaigns, because this means that more people from risk groups will take advantage of colorectal cancer screening tests.
	Low	In the future, politicians could therefore examine which measures could help ensure that more people from risk groups and from the latter's environment will take advantage of vaccination.	In the future, politicians could therefore examine which measures could help to ensure that more people from risk groups will take advantage of colorectal cancer screening tests.

Note: The table contains a translation of the original treatments used to create the quotes. The experiment was conducted in French and German.

Sample

Table A4 Sample description

	Sample		Population ⁱ		
	N	%	N	%	
Sex					
	Female	363	30.5	704	27.9
	Male	828	69.5	1,817	72.1
	N	1,191	100.0	2,517	100.0
Language Region					
	German-speaking	891	74.8	1,856	73.6
	French-speaking	300	25.2	665	26.4
	N	1,191	100.0	2,517	100.0
Political ideology					
	Right-wing	229	20.0	596	24.4
	Center	553	48.4	1,148	47.0
	Left-wing	361	31.6	699	28.6
	N	1,143	100.0	2,413	100.0

Note: One canton (Appenzell Innerrhoden) does not publish its MPs' party affiliations because the composition of its regional parliament occurs along district cubes (n=28). Information about some MPs party affiliations was not available or they consider themselves independent (n=20). Right-wing MPs include members of the Swiss People's Party (SVP) and of smaller right-wing parties (e.g., EDU). Left-wing MPs include members of the Social Democrats (SP), the Green Party, and of smaller left-wing parties (e.g., AL). Centrist MPs include members of the Liberals (FDP), the Conservative Democratic Party (BDP), the Green Liberal Party (GLP), the Christian Democratic People's Party (CVP), and other centrist parties (e.g., EVP)

Randomization

Table A5 Randomization checks across the experimental groups

Vignette		Groups												
		All	3	4	5	6	9	12	14	15	17	18	23	24
<i>Sex (male)</i>		69.5	73.7	72.6	74.5	71.7	67.0	67.7	73.0	57.8	71.6	72.2	73.3	59.0
<i>Age</i>														
	18-39	16.9	19.2	15.8	20.6	18.4	10.4	16.1	11.1	16.7	15.7	11.3	26.9	19.4
	40-64	72.8	69.7	73.7	68.6	69.4	80.2	72.0	80.8	72.5	72.5	77.3	65.4	72.4
	> 64	10.3	11.1	10.5	10.8	12.2	9.4	11.8	8.1	10.8	11.8	11.3	7.7	8.2
<i>Tertiary education</i>		49.9	57.1	45.6	44.3	50.5	49.0	47.8	43.8	54.6	49.0	52.6	56.3	47.5
<i>Ideology</i>														
	Right	20.0	15.8	20.4	25.0	23.5	23.9	24.4	25.0	16.3	19.4	15.1	14.9	17.5
	Center	48.4	53.7	45.2	45.0	45.9	45.5	52.3	38.5	42.9	51.0	58.1	49.5	53.6
	Left	31.6	30.5	34.4	30.0	30.6	30.7	23.3	36.5	40.8	29.6	26.9	35.6	28.9
<i>Accountability (M/SD)</i>		4.2 (1.1)	4.1 (1.1)	4.1 (1.1)	4.2 (1.1)	4.1 (1.0)	4.1 (1.2)	4.2 (1.1)	4.4 (1.0)	4.3 (1.1)	4.2 (1.0)	4.1 (1.1)	4.4 (1.1)	4.2 (1.1)
<i>N</i>		1,191	99	95	102	99	97	93	100	102	102	97	105	100

Note: The table shows that, for example, female MPs, MPs aged between 40 and 64 years, and centrist MPs were overrepresented in some groups. However, Pearson's Chi-squared tests indicate that this overrepresentation did not lead to significant imbalances on specific values of the treatment variables (e.g., that male respondents evaluated quotes from academic experts significantly more often). I also calculated Pearson's Chi-squared for accountability beliefs. The test indicates that there were no significant imbalances on specific values of the treatment variables regarding accountability.

Question wording and summary statistics of the dependent and independent variables

Table A6 Information about the variables used in the analysis

Variable name	Description	Original wording in survey (translated from German/French)
expert credibility (mean additive index)	N=1,191 M=4.97 SD=1.17 Min: 1 Max: 7 $\alpha=0.93$ IIC=0.70	What qualities would you ascribe to the expert quoted? Please make a decision for each adjective pair: [competent/incompetent, well trained/ill-trained, experienced/inexperienced, sincere/insincere, fair/unfair, trustworthy/untrustworthy; scale from 1 to 7]
accountability beliefs (mean additive index)	N=1,190 M=4.19 SD=1.08 Min: 1 Max: 7 $\alpha=0.79$ IIC=0.48	Think about all people who consider voting for your party. To what extent: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are they generally aware of the parliamentary work you personally do? - are they generally aware of your personal position on different issues? - do they know about the outcomes of your political work? - does this knowledge influence these potential voters' decisions at the ballot box? [not at all, 1, 2...7, totally, don't know]
prior attitudes (mean additive index)	<i>Flu:</i> N=605 M=4.43 SD=1.14 Min: 1 Max: 7 $\alpha=0.77$ IIC=0.39 <i>CCS:</i> N=584 M=4.93 SD=0.99	To what extent do you agree with the following statements? <i>Flu vaccination:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The risks of influenza are exaggerated. [reverse coded item] - Flu vaccination is risky. [reverse coded item] - Flu vaccination can effectively prevent influenza. - Instead of getting a flu shot, people had better go through the flu naturally. [reverse coded item] - The pharmaceutical companies in particular are doing business with the scaremongering surrounding flu epidemics. [reverse coded item] <i>Colorectal cancer screening:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The risks of colon cancer are exaggerated. [reverse coded item]

Variable name	Description	Original wording in survey (translated from German/French)
	Min: 1 Max: 7 $\alpha=0.65$ IIC=0.27	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Colorectal cancer screening is risky. [reverse coded item] - Colorectal cancer screening can effectively prevent colon cancer. - Instead of getting screened for colon cancer, people had better maintain a healthy lifestyle. [reverse coded item] - The pharmaceutical companies in particular are making a business out of scaremongering surrounding colon cancer. [reverse coded item] <p>[completely disagree, 1,2,...7 completely agree, don't know]</p>
health policy specialization (dummy variable)	N=1,190 Shares: 0=67.14% 1=32.86%	Would you select health policy as one of your areas of specialization? [yes=1, no=0]
gender (dummy variable)	N=1,191 Shares: male=69.52% female=30.48%	Coded based on mailing list received by parliamentary services
education (dummy variable)	N=1,160 Shares: tertiary=49.91% other=50.09%	<p>What is the highest education or the highest training certificate you have received? [no completed school education, compulsory school, apprenticeship/vocational school, high school/primary teacher training, higher technical and vocational training, higher technical college, university/university of applied sciences, don't know]</p> <p>Recoded into "tertiary education" (i.e., university/university of applied sciences) and "other"</p>
age (continuous variable)	N=1,185 M=51.71 SD=11.02 Min: 22 Max: 81	Coded based on secondary information retrieved from MPs' websites or mailing lists provided by the parliamentary services.

Note: flu=flu vaccination, ccs=colorectal cancer screening

Distribution of accountability beliefs and issue attitudes

Fig. A2 Distribution of accountability beliefs

Note: The figure displays the frequency distribution of the index of accountability beliefs. 1 stands for beliefs in voters’ “weak ability to hold to account,” while 7 denotes belief in voters’ “strong ability to hold to account”.

Fig. A3 Accountability beliefs by ideology

Note: The figure displays MPs' mean accountability beliefs (mean index) by ideology. 1 stands for beliefs in voters' "weak ability to hold to account," while 7 denotes belief in voters' "strong ability to hold to account." Right-wing MPs include members of the Swiss People's Party (SVP) and of smaller right-wing parties (e.g., EDU). Left-wing MPs include members of the Social Democrats (SP), the Green Party, and of smaller left-wing parties (e.g., AL). Center parties include members of the Liberals (FDP), the Conservative Democratic Party (BDP), the Green Liberal Party (GLP), the Christian Democratic People's Party (CVP) and of other center parties (e.g., EVP). The differences between right-wing and centrist MPs ($M_{\text{center}}=4.08$, $M_{\text{right}}=4.53$, $p=0.000$) and between right-wing and left-wing MPs are significant ($M_{\text{left}}=4.14$, $p=0.000$). The difference between left-wing and centrist MPs is not significant ($p=0.380$).

Fig. A4 Distribution of prior attitudes towards flu vaccination

Note: The figure displays the frequency distribution of the index of prior attitudes towards flu vaccination. 1 stands for “weak support for flu vaccination,” while 7 denotes “strong support for flu vaccination.”

Fig. A5 Prior attitudes towards flu vaccination by ideology

Note: The figure displays MPs' mean support (mean index) for flu vaccination by ideology. 1 stands for “weak support for flu vaccination,” while 7 denotes “strong support for flu vaccination”. Right-wing MPs include members of the Swiss People’s Party (SVP) and of smaller right-wing parties (e.g., EDU). Left-wing MPs include members of the Social Democrats (SP), the Green Party, and of smaller left-wing parties (e.g., AL). Center parties include members of the Liberals (FDP), the Conservative Democratic Party (BDP), the Green Liberal Party (GLP), the Christian Democratic People’s Party (CVP) and of other center parties (e.g., EVP). The difference between centrist and right-wing MPs is significant ($M_{\text{center}}=4.61$, $M_{\text{right}}=4.15$, $p=0.001$). The differences between left-wing ($M_{\text{left}}=4.42$) and right-wing ($p=0.093$) and between left-wing and centrist MPs ($p=0.095$) are only significant at the 10% level.

Fig. A6 Distribution of prior attitudes towards colorectal cancer screening

Note: The figure displays the frequency distribution of the index of prior attitudes towards colorectal cancer screening. 1 stands for “weak support for colorectal cancer screening,” while 7 denotes “strong support for colorectal cancer screening”.

Fig. A7 Prior attitudes towards colorectal cancer screening by ideology

Note: The figure displays MPs' mean support (mean index) for colorectal cancer screening by ideology. 1 stands for "weak support for colorectal cancer screening," while 7 denotes "strong support for colorectal cancer screening". Right-wing MPs include members of the Swiss People's Party (SVP) and of smaller right-wing parties (e.g., EDU). Left-wing MPs include members of the Social Democrats (SP), the Green Party, and of smaller left-wing parties (e.g., AL). Center parties include members of the Liberals (FDP), the Conservative Democratic Party (BDP), the Green Liberal Party (GLP), the Christian Democratic People's Party (CVP) and of other center parties (e.g., EVP). The differences between centrist and right-wing ($M_{\text{center}}=4.97$, $M_{\text{right}}=4.72$, $p=0.033$) and between right-wing and left-wing MPs are significant ($M_{\text{left}}=5.04$, $p=0.012$). The difference between centrist and left MPs is not significant ($p=0.483$).

Pretests

A first pretest took place in fall 2018. This pretest sought to test meaning and effectiveness of the planned experimental manipulations (e.g., Do the respondents describe the type of expert as expected?) (Hauser et al., 2018). To do so, I conducted a short survey of 310 Belgian and Swiss university students. The respondents received one of the 12 sampled expert quotations at random. After reading the quote, they answered a series of questions about the manipulation checks (e.g., “Can you remember who the expert whose statement you just read was?”). An open-ended question at the end of the survey collected feedbacks about the quote’s authenticity. The results indicated overall, the manipulations worked quite well. However, the manipulations for the expert type were strengthened in the second pretest because respondents had difficulty recalling the type. Moreover, I also slightly weakened the manipulation for the quote’s evidence base so as not to overpower the other effects. I then discussed the adapted expert quotes and the whole survey in interviews with three former regional (cantonal) MPs. These interviews helped further refine the quotations and the overall survey. Finally, a second pretest conducted at the beginning of 2019 and using the Dynata panel tested the final survey—including the experiment—on a sample of 728 Swiss citizens. In addition to the effectiveness of the manipulations, this pretest also helped validate my measure for expert credibility. This second pretest confirmed the effectiveness of the manipulations of the quote’s expert type and evidence base. Moreover, it allowed me to derive a valid and reliable measure of expert credibility, which is based on six items (see Table A6).

The manipulation checks in the final survey confirmed that the manipulations were effective. Most MPs correctly remembered the affiliation of the expert whose statement they read. MPs most often correctly remembered academic experts (67.5%), followed by administration experts (60.9%), and corporation experts (58.8%). MPs also correctly identified whether the citation was evidence-based or opinion-based ($M_{\text{evidence-based}}=3.83$, $M_{\text{opinion-based}}=4.32$, $p=0.000$),ⁱⁱ perceived experts engaging in high advocacy as more strongly

motivated to persuade than to inform ($M_{\text{advocacy-high}}=3.97$, $M_{\text{advocacy-low}}=4.25$, $p=0.015$),ⁱⁱⁱ and also correctly identified when experts made explicit recommendations ($M_{\text{advocacy-high}}=4.71$) or not ($M_{\text{advocacy-low}}=4.02$, $p=0.000$).

Detailed model output

Table A7 Models of expert credibility: main and interaction effects

	Model 1: Main effects	Model 2: Interaction type of expert	Model 3: Interaction evidence base	Model 4: Interaction advocacy
Intercept	5.03*** (0.10)	5.03*** (0.10)	5.03*** (0.10)	5.03*** (0.10)
<i>Main effects</i>				
Type of expert (Ref.: academic)				
Administration	-0.07 (0.08)	-0.08 (0.08)	-0.06 (0.08)	-0.07 (0.08)
Corporation	-0.35*** (0.08)	-0.36*** (0.08)	-0.35*** (0.08)	-0.36*** (0.08)
Evidence base (evidence-based)	0.19** (0.06)	0.19** (0.06)	0.18** (0.06)	0.18** (0.06)
Advocacy (high)	-0.13* (0.06)	-0.12 ^(.) (0.06)	-0.13* (0.06)	-0.13* (0.06)
Accountability (high)	0.03 (0.03)	0.16** (0.05)	0.09* (0.04)	0.01 (0.04)
<i>Interactions</i>				
Accountability x			-	
Administration/Academic	-	-0.15* (0.07)	-	
Corporation/Academic	-	-0.23*** (0.07)	-	
Accountability x Evidence base	-	-	-0.12* (0.06)	
Accountability x Advocacy				0.06 (0.06)

Table A7 continued

	Model 1: Main effects	Model 2: Interaction type of expert	Model 3: Interaction evidence base	Model 4: Interaction advocacy
<i>Controls</i>				
Flu vaccination	-0.01 (0.06)	-0.01 (0.06)	-0.01 (0.06)	-0.01 (0.06)
Prior attitude (aligned)	0.42*** (0.03)	0.41*** (0.03)	0.41*** (0.03)	0.42*** (0.03)
Specialized in health policy	0.00 (0.07)	0.01 (0.07)	0.00 (0.07)	0.00 (0.07)
Gender (male)	-0.03 (0.07)	-0.03 (0.07)	-0.02 (0.07)	-0.03 (0.07)
Education (tertiary)	0.16* (0.06)	0.17** (0.06)	0.16* (0.06)	0.16* (0.06)
Age	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
R ²	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.20
Adj. R ²	0.19	0.20	0.19	0.19
N	1,151	1,151	1,151	1,151
RMSE (normalized)	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17

***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05, ^cp<0.1.

Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) from linear regression models (OLS). The variables ‘accountability’, ‘prior attitude’ and ‘age’ were centered.

Additional models

Table A8 Models excluding MPs who failed the manipulation checks

	Model 1: Main effects	Model 2: Interaction effect	Model 3: Interaction effect	Model 4: Interaction effect
Intercept	5.31*** (0.20)	5.12*** (0.12)	4.88*** (0.13)	5.10*** (0.13)
<i>Main effects</i>				
Type of expert (Ref.: academic)				
Administration	-0.37* (0.15)	-0.16 ^(c) (0.09)	-0.07 (0.09)	-0.12 (0.10)
Corporation	-0.69*** (0.15)	-0.57*** (0.09)	-0.35*** (0.09)	-0.35*** (0.10)
Evidence base (evidence-based)	0.46*** (0.13)	0.25*** (0.07)	0.43*** (0.08)	0.19* (0.08)
Advocacy (high)	-0.23 ^(c) (0.13)	-0.11 (0.07)	-0.20** (0.08)	-0.17* (0.08)
Accountability (high)	0.07 (0.06)	0.16** (0.06)	0.08 (0.05)	0.07 (0.06)

Table A8 continued

	Model 1: Main effects	Model 2: Interaction effect	Model 3: Interaction effect	Model 4: Interaction effect
<i>Interactions</i>				
Accountability x				
Administration/Academic		-0.12 (0.09)		
Corporation/Academic		-0.23* (0.09)		
Accountability x Evidence base	-	-	-0.14 ^(c) (0.07)	
Accountability x Advocacy	-	-	-	-0.04 (0.08)
R ²	0.27	0.26	0.24	0.21
Adj. R ²	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.19
N	274	716	696	672
RMSE (normalized)	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.17

Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) from linear regression models (OLS). The models only include MPs who did not fail the manipulation checks. Only MPs who passed the manipulation checks for all treatment variables (i.e., type of expert, evidence base and advocacy) were included in the sample for model 1. Only MPs who failed the manipulation check for the treatment variable in the interaction were excluded from the samples for the models with the interaction effects. The variable ‘accountability’ was centered. Not reported are the coefficients of the control variables ‘issue,’ ‘prior attitude,’ ‘specialization,’ ‘gender,’ ‘education,’ and ‘age’.

Table A9 Models with ideology as an additional control variable

	Model 1: Main effects	Model 2: Interaction effect	Model 3: Interaction effect	Model 4: Interaction effect
Intercept	4.95*** (0.12)	4.95*** (0.12)	4.95*** (0.12)	4.96*** (0.12)
<i>Main effects</i>				
Type of expert (Ref.: academic)				
Administration	-0.06 (0.08)	-0.07 (0.08)	-0.05 (0.08)	-0.06 (0.08)
Corporation	-0.35*** (0.08)	-0.36*** (0.08)	-0.35*** (0.08)	-0.35*** (0.08)
Evidence base (evidence-based)	0.18** (0.06)	0.19** (0.06)	0.18** (0.06)	0.18** (0.06)
Advocacy (high)	-0.13* (0.06)	-0.13* (0.06)	-0.13* (0.06)	-0.13* (0.06)
Accountability (high)	0.02 (0.03)	0.16** (0.05)	0.08 ⁽⁻⁾ (0.04)	0.00 (0.04)
<i>Interactions</i>				
Accountability x				
Administration/Academic	-	-0.19** (0.07)	-	-
Corporation/Academic	-	-0.23** (0.07)	-	-
Accountability x Evidence base	-	-	-0.12* (0.06)	-
Accountability x Advocacy	-	-	-	0.05 (0.06)

Table A9 continued

	Model 1: Main effects	Model 2: Interaction effect	Model 3: Interaction effect	Model 4: Interaction effect
<i>Controls</i>				
Ideology (Ref.: right-wing)				
Centrist	0.04 (0.09)	0.05 (0.09)	0.05 (0.09)	0.04 (0.09)
Left-wing	0.16 (0.10)	0.18 ^(.) (0.10)	0.16 ^(.) (0.10)	0.16 (0.10)
R ²	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.20
Adj. R ²	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.19
N	1,105	1,105	1,105	1,105
RMSE (normalized)	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.18

Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) from linear regression models (OLS). The variable ‘accountability’ was centered. The models contain the six control variables (issue, prior attitude, specialization, gender, education, age) plus ‘ideology’ as an additional control variable. Out of all control variables, only the coefficients for ideology are reported. Right-wing MPs include members of the Swiss People’s Party (SVP) and of smaller right-wing parties (e.g., EDU). Left-wing MPs include members of the Social Democrats (SP), the Green Party and of smaller left-wing parties (e.g., AL). Centrist MPs include members of the Liberals (FDP), the Conservative Democratic Party (BDP), the Green Liberal Party (GLP), the Christian Democratic People’s Party (CVP), and other centrist parties (e.g., EVP).

Table A10 Linear main-effects models by issue

	Model 1: Flu	Model 2: CCS
Intercept	4.89*** (0.13)	5.18*** (0.15)
<i>Main effects</i>		
Type of expert (Ref.: academic)		
Administration	-0.05 (0.11)	-0.09 (0.11)
Corporation	-0.34** (0.10)	-0.37*** (0.11)
Evidence base (evidence-based)	0.29** (0.09)	0.09 (0.10)
Advocacy (high)	-0.18* (0.09)	-0.15 (0.10)
Accountability (high)	0.06 (0.04)	0.00 (0.04)
<i>Controls</i>		
Prior attitude (aligned)	0.39*** (0.04)	0.43*** (0.05)
Specialized in health policy	0.00 (0.10)	0.00 (0.10)
Gender (male)	0.01 (0.10)	-0.07 (0.10)
Education (tertiary)	0.28** (0.09)	0.04 (0.09)
Age	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
R ²	0.22	0.17
Adj. R ²	0.21	0.15
N	588	563
RMSE (normalized)	0.17	0.18

***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05, [†]p<0.1.

Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) from linear regression models (OLS). The variables ‘accountability,’ ‘prior attitude,’ and ‘age’ were centered. CCS=colorectal cancer screening.

Fig. A8 Effect of type of expert on credibility by accountability and issue

Note: Panel A displays the effect expert type exerts on perceived expert credibility for each issue as accountability beliefs vary. Panel B plots the mean predicted values of expert credibility by expert type and for different levels of accountability and for each issue. Weak=3.11 (mean-1 standard deviation), moderate=4.19 (mean), strong=5.27 (mean+1 standard deviation).

Fig. A9 Effect of evidence base on credibility by accountability and issue

Note: Panel A displays the effect of the evidence base on perceived expert credibility for each issue as accountability beliefs vary. Panel B plots the mean predicted values of expert credibility by evidence base for different levels of accountability and for each issue. Weak=3.11 (mean-1 standard deviation), moderate=4.19 (mean), strong=5.27 (mean+1 standard deviation).

Fig. A10 Effect of advocacy on credibility by accountability and issue

Note: Panel A displays the effect of advocacy on perceived expert credibility for each issue as accountability beliefs vary. Panel B plots the mean predicted values of expert credibility by degree of advocacy for different levels of accountability and for each issue. Weak=3.11 (mean-1 standard deviation), moderate=4.19 (mean), strong=5.27 (mean+1 standard deviation).

References

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- i The population consists of all MPs that were contacted for the survey.
 - ii Lower numbers indicate “evidence-based,” while higher numbers denote “opinion-based.”
 - iii Lower numbers indicate “motivated to persuade,” while higher numbers denote “motivated to inform.”